

Estimation of the cost of budget services provided to budget organizations (institutions)

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***Аннотация.** Ушбу мақолада byudjet tashkilotlariga (muassasalariga) ko'rsatiladigan byudjet xizmatlari qiymatini baholashni янада такомиллаштиришига қаратилган илмий таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.*

***Калим сўзлар:** давлат молияси, byudjet tashkiloti, маҳаллий бюджет, даромад, инвестицион лойиҳа, барқарорлик.*

***Аннотация.** В данной статье разработаны научные предложения, направленные на дальнейшее совершенствование оценки стоимости бюджетных услуг, предоставляемых бюджетным организациям (учреждениям).*

***Ключевые слова:** государственные финансы, бюджетная организация, местный бюджет, доходы, инвестиционный проект, стабильность.*

***Abstract:** In this article, scientific proposals aimed at further improving the assessment of the value of budget services provided to budget organizations (institutions) have been developed.*

***Keywords:** state finance, budget organization, local budget, income, investment project, stability.*

Estimating the cost of a budget service involves calculating the effectiveness of budget costs, based on the ratio of the cost of the budget service produced and the budget costs for its provision.

This method indicates the possibility of assessing budget expenditures for their ability to create additional value, i.e. assess the level of their synergy. Moreover, we are talking about the commensurability of the value of a good provided to budgetary entities free of charge for consumers, and a good that can be purchased from small businesses. The list of such services is quite large: preschool, general, specialized secondary, higher education, provision of medical services, cultural services.

This method most fully characterizes the efficiency of using budget funds, but its use may be limited for two reasons. Firstly, many of the listed services are provided by the budgetary institutions themselves, but on a paid basis. The price is calculated based on the cost of the components, and therefore in this market segment you can find out how much the service costs, but not how much it should cost. The value of any budget service must be greater than the cost of its components, and the rate of return is set by the market, not by the provider of the budget service.

Secondly, there is no market for a number of budget services due to the imperfection of existing market relations.

Any limitation in the application of this method constitutes its disadvantage. However, this disadvantage can be mitigated through competitive distribution of funds both between public sector institutions and private businesses.

The most optimal use of this method is to assess the effectiveness of budget expenditures for the provision of budget services that have an analogue on the market. Expanding the practice of creating and operating autonomous budgetary institutions will make it possible to apply this method to a large number of types of budgetary

activities. In the future, the use of this method is necessary to assess the effectiveness of the most popular budget services among the population - education, health, culture [1]. This method can be applied within the framework of both traditional budgeting in order to control the unreasonable increase in budget expenditures, and within the framework of result-oriented budgeting in order to identify and finance the services most in demand among the population.

Consequently, efficiency assessment methods, which consist of converting the results of budget expenditures into monetary equivalents, are focused on comparing the results of budget expenditures with the results of the commercial sector.

So, the efficiency of government spending lags behind the efficiency of business spending. Therefore, the withdrawal of resources from the commercial sector into the budget system (through taxes, duties, fees, excise taxes, etc.) reduces the efficiency of the country's economy as a whole.

The effectiveness of budget expenditures can be assessed by reducing costs and results to a single indicator. For the methods of correlation of conditional efficiencies involves the ratio of the conditional efficiency of budgetary expenditures of a budgetary institution for the provision of a certain budgetary service and the conditional efficiency of a similar institution for the provision of this budgetary service[2].

Hence, conditional efficiency may imply the ratio of the result (both in quantitative and qualitative dimensions) and the budgetary costs associated with its production, expressed in various units of change.

For example, the result of providing general education services at a lyceum can be measured in average scores, the number of students admitted to universities, and test results. The listed indicators (indicators) can be ranked, their conditional

significance determined, evaluated in points, and after adding up the points scored for all indicators, a final score can be obtained, which will be the assessment of the result. The ratio of the total final score to costs (per student) is the conditional efficiency of spending budget funds to provide budget services at the lyceum (let's call it lyceum No. 1). In another similar lyceum No. 2, the results will be different, in some ways they will exceed the results of lyceum No. 1, and in others they will be inferior. Whoever has this indicator higher can ensure more efficient spending of budget funds[3].

For comparison, the average indicator for all similar institutions or an option recognized and established as a criterion can be taken as a basis.

If the advantage of this method is its focus on identifying “lagging” subjects from the average, or from the state being made. At the same time, the identification of ineffective spending of budget funds is ensured promptly and with minimal costs, but the disadvantage of the method is manifested in the subjectivity of ranking indicators of the performance of a budgetary institution: the number of excellent students or those entering universities and colleges), the development of their creative abilities or the number of successful performances at olympiads - which is more important and how much.

In our opinion, the most optimal use of this method will be acceptable if it is based on planned and normative budgeting indicators and is result-oriented.

List of used literature

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